

Benchmark Evaluation of a Cannabinoid Drug Interaction Chatbot

Yifan Liu¹, Dima Rabadi, PhD², Paul T. Kocis, PharmD, MPH³

¹ Software Engineering Student, The Pennsylvania State University (PSU), Erie, PA

² Assistant Professor of Cybersecurity Analytics and Operations, The Pennsylvania State University (PSU), Sharon, PA

³ Assistant Professor of Neuroscience & Experimental Therapeutics, The Pennsylvania State University (PSU), College of Medicine, Hershey, PA

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR:

Paul T. Kocis, PharmD, RPh, MPH
Assistant Professor, Dept of Neuroscience & Experimental Therapeutics,
Penn State College of Medicine, Hershey, PA

Clinical Pharmacist, Anticoagulation Clinic, Milton S. Hershey Medical Center,
Penn State Health, Hershey, PA

Email: puk4@psu.edu

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Large Language Model (LLM), chatbot, cannabinoid, CBD, THC, CANN-DIR, Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG), Clinical Decision Support (CDS), artificial intelligence (AI), Drug Interaction

KEY POINTS

Question

How does the Cannabinoid Drug Interaction (CDI) Chatbot perform when compared to other well-known Large Language Models (LLMs)?

Findings

The Cannabinoid Drug Interaction (CDI) Chatbot combines an LLM, an embedding model, a specialized drug knowledge database, web search capabilities and a unified retrieval augmented generation (RAG) framework to answer cannabinoid drug interaction questions. The performance of the CDI was validated using a dataset of 1,369 multiple-choice questions across a variety of medical topics.

Meaning

The CDI chatbot (a RAG-based system) demonstrates > 90% accuracy in correctly answering cannabinoid drug-drug interaction (DDI) questions, outperforming isolated LLMs without RAG.

ABSTRACT

IMPORTANCE

Large Language Models (LLMs) have enabled chatbots, such as the Cannabinoid Drug Interaction (CDI) chatbot, to leverage patterns learned from training on vast datasets to formulate a response. The CDI also demonstrates adaptability in answering broader medical and other non-cannabinoid drug interaction inquiries.

OBJECTIVE

To evaluate the Cannabinoid Drug Interaction (CDI) Chatbot with standard benchmarking datasets and compare to other well-known LLMs.

DESIGN, SETTING, AND PARTICIPANTS

The CDI implements a retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) framework that integrates the Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct LLM for text generation and the gte-large-en-v1.5 embedding model

for prompt classification. This combination of models allows for efficient hybrid information retrieval from database and web-based search results. Additionally, the CDI chatbot accesses a specialized cannabinoid drug interaction knowledge database.

INTERVENTION

LLM and embedding benchmark testing was used to evaluate the performance of the CDI chatbot.

MAIN OUTCOMES AND MEASURES

A benchmarking dataset, containing 280 multiple-choice cannabinoid focused questions, was developed to evaluate the CDI chatbot. The benchmarking of CDI also utilized Massive Multitask Language Understanding (MMLU) datasets to establish a standard point of reference accessed through the open source LLM evaluation framework DeepEval.

RESULTS

When drug database context was included, cannabinoid DDI accuracy scores were more than doubled when compared to the LLM-only performance of gemma-2-9b-it and Mistral-NeMo-12B-Instruct models. The gemma-2-9b-it with retrieval from drug database and web sources, using the gte-large-en-v1.5 embedding model, achieved 80% accuracy in MMLU Clinical Knowledge (CK) and 90% accuracy in MMLU Medical Genetics (MG) tasks. These scores are comparable to the LLM-only results of the Meta-Llama-3-70B-Instruct, which scored 79.62% on MMLU Clinical Knowledge (CK) and 90% on MMLU Medical Genetics (MG) tasks. The CDI chatbot exhibited robust retrieval capabilities for cannabinoid DDI information, with 269 out of 280 context instances scoring above 0.9 for contextual precision and 278 out of 280 context instances scoring above 0.9 for contextual relevancy. The CDI chatbot achieved > 90% accuracy in correctly answering cannabinoid drug-drug interaction (DDI) questions; thereby, outperforming other LLMs tested.

CONCLUSIONS AND RELEVANCE

The Cannabinoid Drug Interaction (CDI) Chatbot demonstrates promising results for providing reliable and accurate DDI information for the cannabinoid class of medications. The CDI chatbot underscores the potential of a RAG framework to advance clinical decision support (CDS) to provide accurate, context-aware drug interaction information. Further validation would be needed to assess suitability for clinical decision support deployments.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Large Language Models (LLMs) are trained on large amounts of data that contain billions of data parameters. Benchmarking is an automated standardized process to quantitatively evaluate the different AI models. The increased availability of LLMs has also normalized user engagement with chatbots that generate original output when formulating an answer to a question and thus function as a clinical decision support (CDS) tool.

The Cannabinoid Drug Interaction (CDI) chatbot employs the Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct¹ large language model (LLM), integrates natural language processing with the gte-large-en-v1.5² embedding model,³ and utilize vectors to represent textual data (e.g., written or spoken words). This then allows for hybrid information retrieval for database and web-based searches.

The CDI chatbot also implements a retrieval augmented generation (RAG) framework to allow for additional databases to be included without needing to retrain the LLM. This allows for accurate, personalized, and context-aware original output to perform as a cannabinoid clinical decision support tool.⁴ Context is defined as the information that the generative AI model considers when generating a response.⁵

As illustrated in Figure 1, the CDI chatbot employs a four-stage process comprised of: (1) User Interaction, (2) Classification/Semantic Routing, (3) Information Retrieval, and then (4) Response Generation. The initial phase begins with User Interaction to formulate a query that is stored in a conversation history array and then sent to the embedding model to calculate similarity scores needed for classification. In the Classification/Semantic Routing phase, the system classifies the user's query into one of the four types: Chitchat, Guardrails, Web Search, and Database Search.

Based on the user's type of query classification, the system proceeds with semantic routing, calling the corresponding function for context retrieval. Information Retrieval involves an online Web Search. The utilization of a *'drug_interaction_finder'* function to interface with the Cannabinoid Drug Interaction Review (CANN-DIR[®]) database employs RapidFuzz⁶ string matching to compare the user's query against medication names. Lastly, the CDI chatbot combines the user query, along with the context produced during the retrieval step, to compose a type of prompt sent to the LLM for Response Generation. Depending on the query classification and semantic routing, the chatbot supports three distinct prompt types. The Type 1 prompt (ChitChat) integrates a system directive for query types categorized as general small talk (e.g., *'How are you?'* or *'Is it cold outside?'*) topics unrelated to the medical domain.

Figure 1: Proposed Framework for the Cannabinoid Drug Interaction (CDI) Chatbot

Legend:

- API (Application Programming Interface)
- CANN-DIR® (CANNabinoid Drug Interaction Review)
- CDI (Cannabinoid Drug Interaction)
- DDGS (DuckDuckGo Search)
- LLM (Large Language Model)

The Type 2 prompt (Guardrails) addresses unacceptable use cases that include jailbreaks (techniques that bypass LLM safety measures) and inappropriate language. The Type 3 prompt (Contextual Queries) retrieves information from an online web search or specialized knowledge database.

2. Methods

After applying standard data cleaning techniques (e.g., removing duplicates, addressing missing values, correcting for inconsistencies, and filtering out irrelevant or noisy data), the scraped data from CANN-DIR® was processed using the Meta-Llama-3.1-405B-Instruct⁷ LLM.

Benchmarking, an automated standardized process to quantitatively evaluate different AI models⁸, was then utilized to evaluate different configurations of the LLM and embedding

Table 1: Benchmark Dataset

Dataset	Sample Questions (N=1,369)	Dataset Description
MMLU ^a Clinical Knowledge (CK)	265	Clinical Knowledge (CK) multiple-choice questions
MMLU ^a Anatomy (A)	135	Anatomy (A) multiple-choice questions
MMLU ^a Medical Genetics (MG)	100	Medical Genetics (MG) multiple-choice questions
MMLU ^a Professional Medicine (PM)	272	Professional Medicine (PM) multiple-choice questions
MMLU ^a College Medicine (CM)	173	College Medicine (CM) multiple-choice questions
MMLU ^a College Biology (CB)	144	College Biology (CB) multiple-choice questions
CANN-DIR ^b DDI ^c -cannabidiol (CBD)	70	Cannabidiol (CBD) DDI multiple-choice questions
CANN-DIR ^b DDI ^c -nabiximols	70	Nabiximols DDI multiple-choice questions
CANN-DIR ^b DDI ^c -dronabinol	70	Dronabinol DDI multiple-choice questions
CANN-DIR ^b DDI ^c -nabilone	70	Nabilone DDI multiple-choice questions

Legend:

^aMassive Multitask Language Understanding (MMLU)

^bCannabinoid Drug Interaction Review (CANN-DIR[®])

^cDrug-Drug Interaction (DDI)

model in the CDI chatbot on synthetic datasets of the four precipitant medications: cannabidiol, dronabinol, nabilone, and nabiximols.^{8,9} The benchmarking dataset (Table 1), generated by the Meta-Llama-3.1-405B-Instruct LLM, contains 280 multiple-choice cannabinoid focused questions to evaluate the CDI chatbot.

In order to establish a standard point of reference, the benchmarking of CDI also evaluated the Massive Multitask Language Understanding (MMLU) datasets accessed through the open source LLM evaluation framework DeepEval.¹⁰ These MMLU datasets contain approximately 16,000 questions from among 57 various subject areas (e.g., ethics, history, law, medical) in which 6 of the medical related datasets were utilized.¹⁰

2.1 Benchmark Evaluation

The open source DeepEval LLM was the primary evaluation framework used in this study.¹¹ Our custom designed benchmark model was then integrated into DeepEval to analyze and measure LLM output quality Answer Relevancy (AR) & Answer Faithfulness (AF) as well as retrieval context quality (Contextual Precision & Contextual Recall) for the CDI chatbot RAG system.¹¹ These above-mentioned benchmarking terms are further defined along with the calculation formulas located in the supplementary material (Table S1).^{12,13}

Cannabinoid DDI and MMLU questions were rephrased as open-ended questions when incorporated into the three small LLMs: Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct¹, gemma-2-9b-it¹⁴, and the Mistral-NeMo-12B-Instruct.¹⁵ Instead of human intervention, an LLM was utilized (aka: 'LLM as a Judge'¹⁶) to measure the output of another LLM; therefore, evaluates and identifies relevant statements to calculate metrics under consistent evaluation criteria.¹⁷

2.2 LLM Benchmarking

The standardized prompt format used for the LLM generation benchmarking are: Task Introduction, Few-Shot examples, Additional Context, and Benchmarking Questions. The Task Introduction provides a concise overview of the problem and sets the context for the subsequent components. The system prompt, that allowed for the creation of the cannabinoid DDI benchmark dataset, is placed in Figure 2.

When relevant, Few-Shot examples^{18,19} provide a limited number of examples to help guide the model's understanding and performance. These examples act as reference points for the desired output format and content. Additional Context from database or web sources is

specifically designed for RAG benchmarking scenarios, providing supplementary information to enhance the model's contextual understanding of the task. Benchmarking Questions present the core question or task for evaluation, designed to assess the model or RAG system's performance.

Figure 2: System Prompt Allowing for Creation of the Cannabinoid DDI Benchmark Dataset

```
[
  {"role": "system", "content": ""You are an AI language model designed to create challenging multiple-choice questions for an MMLU benchmark dataset on drug-drug interactions of cannabinoids. Given a fact about the interaction between two medications, you will generate a question, four answer choices, and indicate the correct answer choice. Mention specific UGT and CYP enzymes in the answer choices when applicable. The output should be in the following fixed format:
Input: A fact about the interaction between two drugs.
Output:
{
  "question": "Question text here (Do not mention Cann-DIR®)",
  "choices": [
    "A) Choice A text here",
    "B) Choice B text here",
    "C) Choice C text here",
    "D) Choice D text here"
  ],
  "correct_answer": "Correct choice text here"
}""},
  {"role": "user", "content": input_text}
]
```

2.3 Embedding Model Benchmarking

The benchmarking process embedding model follows a custom framework with three main steps: Encoding, Inference, and Accuracy calculation. During the Encoding step, there are semantic router utterances,^{20,21} defined as possible user inputs (e.g., *'What is the drug interaction between ...'*), vectorized by the embedding model that provide a point of reference for comparison against real user or benchmarking questions. During the Inference step, the benchmark dataset (containing 1,369 test questions) is passed through each embedding model; thereupon, to calculate the similarity of each vectorized question compared to vectorized semantic router utterances and evaluate router classifications. The last step of Accuracy, compares the route classifications with the optimal ones. The optimal route classification for the MMLU clinical topics dataset is via the 'Web Search' route and for the optimal route cannabinoid DDI dataset is via the 'Interactions' route. The classification of each question will determine if additional context will be retrieved during the RAG benchmarking process and then provided to the LLM for response generation.

3. RESULTS

A thorough analysis and evaluation of pre-trained LLMs, embedding models, and RAG systems was performed. The performance of the seven Large Language Models (LLMs) and the five embedding models were compared to a variety of benchmarking datasets to observe their efficacy across different medical datasets. The Small LLMs, ≤ 15 billion parameter models, were then compared to the Meta-Llama-3-70B-Instruct.

The performance impact of the RAG framework was assessed by benchmarking three LLMs (Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct, gemma-2-9b-it, and Mistral-NeMo-12B-Instruct) on the same seven datasets, (See Table 4).

3.1 Embedding Models

Embedding AI models use vectors to represent data (e.g., text, image, video)³ and were benchmarked before RAG system benchmarking. In order to determine the optimal embedding model to be utilized in the RAG system, all 1,369 test questions, across the MMLU clinical topics

Table 2: Embedding Models Benchmark Comparison

	gte-large-en-v1.5	mxbai-embed-large-v1	stella_en_400M_v5	bge-large-en-v1.5	snowflake-arctic-embed-l
Cannabinoid DDI ^a Dataset	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	98.6
MMLU ^b Clinical Knowledge (CK) Dataset	24.2 (Web Search only) 80.4 (with None)	51.3 (Web Search only) 63.8 (with None)	54.0 * Null none	50.9 52.8	56.2 * Null none
MMLU ^b Medical Genetics (MG) Dataset	37.0 (Web Search only) 77.0 (with None)	59.0 67.0	56.0 57.0	53.0 * Null none	38.0 * Null none
MMLU ^b Anatomy (A) Dataset	25.2 (Web Search only) 90.4 (with None)	59.2 76.3	63.7 64.4	62.2 64.4	55.6 * Null none
MMLU ^b Professional Medicine (PM) Dataset	31.2 (Web Search only) 68.8 (with None)	66.5 72.8	36.0 37.1	68.0 68.4	62.1 * Null none
MMLU ^b College Biology (CB) Dataset	23.6 (Web Search only) 80.1 (with None)	66.0 72.2	50.0 51.4	66.7 67.4	23.6 * Null none

MMLU ^b	31.8 (Web Search only)	57.2	44.5	57.2	39.3
College Medicine (CM) Dataset	66.5 (with None)	66.5	46.8	59.0	39.9

Legend:

^aDrug-Drug Interaction (DDI)

^bMassive Multitask Language Understanding (MMLU)

and cannabinoid DDI datasets, were inputted to each of the five embedding models with no additional modification, (Table 2). Also, from the results, gte-large-en-v1.5 scored the highest accuracy across all datasets when classifications with the ‘None’ route were reclassified into the ‘Web Search’ route. The term ‘None’ route is a system fallback mechanism where queries that cannot be confidently classified into any predefined route (classified as ‘None’) are automatically redirected to the ‘Web Search’ route.

The underlying rationale is to utilize the ‘Web Search’ route as a universal fallback route capable of addressing a wide range of query types, and to facilitate informed routing decisions in the presence of uncertainty. With this revision, gte-large-en-v1.5 and mxbai-embed-large-v1 achieved accuracy scores > 60.0% across all datasets, reflecting consistent performance among other evaluated models. It is important to note that these accuracy scores are contingent upon the quality of example route objects used in the semantic router library; therefore, variations in data quality could significantly influence model accuracy.

All five embedding models evaluated were of comparable size, each containing approximately 300-400 million parameters; therefore, suggesting that differences in performance are not solely based on model size. The gte-large-en-v1.5 Routing Contextual Precision Metrics, Relevancy Metrics, and Recall Metrics are further described in the supplementary material Table S5, Table S6, and Table S7, respectively.

3.2 LLM Only Baseline Performance

The Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct¹ emerged as the top performer with 54.64% accuracy, surpassing larger models, (Table 3).²² The 70B Llama-based models and gemma model delivered

Table 3: LLM-Only Benchmark Comparison

	OpenBio LLM-8B	Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct	Gemma-2-9b-it	Mistral-NeMo-1 2B-Instruct	Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	Palmyra-Med-70B	Meta-Llama-3-70B-Instruct
Cannabinoid DDI ^a dataset	27.86	54.64	41.79	23.93	26.07	39.64	40.00
MMLU ^b Clinical Knowledge (CN) Dataset	76.10	74.72	74.72 (5-shot)	68.68 (5-shot)	59.62 (5-shot)	90.90	79.62 (5-shot)
MMLU ^b Medical Genetics (MG) Dataset	86.10	83.00	83.00 (5-shot)	73.00 (5-shot)	65.00 (5-shot)	94.00	90.00 (5-shot)
MMLU ^b Anatomy (A) Dataset	69.83	68.89	65.93 (5-shot)	60.74 (5-shot)	52.59 (5-shot)	83.70	77.04 (5-shot)
MMLU ^b Professional Medicine (PM) Dataset	78.21	70.22	74.63 (5-shot)	69.49 (5-shot)	61.40 (5-shot)	92.70	89.34 (5-shot)
MMLU ^b College Biology (CB) Dataset	84.21	78.47	87.50 (5-shot)	75.69 (5-shot)	61.81 (5-shot)	94.40	92.36 (5-shot)
MMLU ^b College Medicine (CM) Dataset	68.04	60.12	69.36 (5-shot)	64.74 (5-shot)	51.45 (5-shot)	84.40	73.99 (5-shot)

Legend:^aDrug-Drug Interaction (DDI)^bMassive Multitask Language Understanding (MMLU)

moderate accuracy (39.64% & 41.79%, respectively), while the Mistral models performed poorly at 23.93%. Despite being based on the high-performing Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct, OpenBioLLM-8B only achieved 27.86% accuracy.²² Among smaller models, OpenBioLLM-8B²³ shows consistency across clinical categories, leading in all areas except in the MMLU College Biology (CB) dataset. For the MMLU clinical topics, Palmyra-Med-70B²⁴ consistently achieved the highest results on all datasets.

3.3 Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) Benchmark Comparison

Notably, 1,189 out of the 1,369 responses from the gemma-2-9b-it model with context achieved an accuracy greater than 0.7, underscoring strong Answer Relevancy (AR). However, context quality remains an area for improvement, with 480 instances scoring a precision between 0 and 0.1. Additionally, the CDI chatbot exhibited robust retrieval capabilities for cannabinoid DDI information, with 269 out of 280 context instances scoring above 0.9 for Contextual Precision (CP) and 278 out of 280 context instances scoring above 0.9 for Contextual Relevancy (CR).

The results in Table 4 show that with the addition of RAG more than doubled the accuracy of gemma-2-9b-it and Mistral-NeMo-12B-Instruct LLMs on cannabinoid drug interaction queries

Table 4: Small LLMs (≤ 15 billion parameters) Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) Benchmark Comparison

	Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct + gte-large-en-v1.5	Gemma-2-9b-it + gte-large-en-v1.5	Mistral-NeMo-12B-Instruct + gte-large-en-v1.5
Cannabinoid DDI ^a Dataset	88.93	90.71	81.07
MMLU ^b Clinical Knowledge (CK) Dataset	77.73 (5-shot + context)	80.00 (5-shot + context)	71.70 (5-shot + context)
MMLU ^b Medical	82.00	90.00	76.00

Genetics (MG) Dataset	(5-shot + context)	(5-shot + context)	(5-shot + context)
MMLU ^b Anatomy (A) Dataset	70.37 (5-shot + context)	71.85 (5-shot + context)	69.62 (5-shot + context)
MMLU ^b Professional Medicine (PM) Dataset	69.11 (5-shot + context)	72.43 (5-shot + context)	73.53 (5-shot + context)
MMLU ^b College Biology (CB) Dataset	77.78 (5-shot + context)	84.03 (5-shot + context)	77.78 (5-shot + context)
MMLU ^b College Medicine (CM) Dataset	66.47 (5-shot + context)	72.25 (5-shot + context)	64.74 (5-shot + context)

Legend:

^aDrug-Drug Interaction (DDI)

^bMassive Multitask Language Understanding (MMLU)

compared to the LLM-only performance of these models (Table 3). As for the Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct, there was a 34.29% decrease (88.93% - 54.64%) in accuracy for cannabinoid drug interaction queries when comparing the performance of the model with RAG, (Table 4, to its LLM-only performance (Table 3). In all benchmark results except MMLU Professional Medicine (PM), gemma-2-9b-it with context demonstrated superior performance compared to Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct and Mistral-NeMo-12B-Instruct LLMs.

The inclusion of context led to marginal performance degradation for Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct and gemma-2-9b-it models, specifically in MMLU Professional Medicine (PM) and MMLU College Biology (CB) datasets. Additionally, some sensitive queries in the MMLU clinical topics datasets were routed to guardrails, resulting in warning messages being relayed to the LLM instead of relevant context.

The Open Response Answer Faithfulness (AF) and Answer Relevancy (AR) Metrics for (Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct + gte-large-en-v1.5); (gemma-2-9b-it + gte-large-en-v1.5); and

(Mistral-NeMo-12B-Instruct + gte-large-en-v1.5) are further described in the supplementary material Table S2, Table S3, and Table S4, respectively.

4. Discussion

The CDI clinical decision support chatbot demonstrates the potential to leverage small scale LLMs to access cannabinoid drug interaction information, and also a broader applicability for general medical and pharmacy related inquiries. The inclusion of retrieval context allowed models such as gemma-2-9b-it to match the LLM-only performance of Meta-Llama-3-70B-Instruct on MMLU Clinical Knowledge (CK) and MMLU Medical Genetics (MG). This study has also shown that the accuracy of small LLMs on cannabinoid drug interaction queries can be increased by more than 30% through the inclusion of a specialized cannabinoid drug interaction database.

LLMs can also provide drug information for pharmacists, with ChatGPT-4 accuracy rates meeting passing criteria on the Japanese National Examination for Pharmacists (JNEP).²⁵ ChatGPT-4 achieved 64.3% full accuracy in inquiries about drug dosing, drug interactions, pregnancy, and lactation, setting benchmarks comparable to human pharmacy professionals.²⁶ However, comparative analyses revealed that human practitioners demonstrated superior capabilities in drug interaction evaluations relative to ChatGPT-4, suggesting opportunities for further improvement through fine-tuning and RAG frameworks.²⁶

The Medication Extraction and Drug Interaction Chatbot (MEDIC) presents a drug interaction tool that uses Optical Character Recognition (OCR) and text similarity techniques to extract drug names from uploaded images.²⁷

A comprehensive cross-sectional study evaluated Microsoft's Bing AI copilot's performance in providing drug information, revealing significant concerns regarding patient safety and information accessibility.²⁸ To address these potential safety issues, medical LLMs can be optimized through fine-tuning that preserves their core abilities while enhancing safety and alignment.²⁹ Med-PaLM 2 uses instruction fine-tuning from the base Pathways Language Model (PaLM) model, consisting of 5 datasets, to create a unified model that matched or exceeded the capabilities of ChatGPT-4 on MMLU clinical topics benchmarks.⁸

Palmyra-Med-70B³⁰ and OpenBioLLM-70B⁹, which is based on Meta-Llama-3-70B-Instruct, utilize the Direct Preference Optimization (DPO) fine-tuning technique to achieve consistent

performance on medical benchmarks.¹⁰ These models improve the performance of Med-PaLM 2 on the same benchmarks highlighting a trend of increasing general medical LLM performance. The Med42³¹, based on Llama 2, and GatorTronGPT³² based on GPT-3 architecture, are models that underscore the efficacy of full-parameter fine-tuning and training from scratch, respectively.

Both these models demonstrate that comprehensive medical training data can yield strong performance on clinical benchmarks. The use of general AI chatbots for predicting drug-drug interaction shows that Bing AI, with an accuracy of (0.890) and a specificity of (0.892) markedly outperformed ChatGPT-3.5, ChatGPT-4, and Bard.³³ It is hypothesized that Bing AI's superior performance can be attributed to its integration with real-time capabilities and web search.³³

5. LIMITATIONS

Despite the strong performance of CDI chatbot in answering cannabinoid medical and drug interaction questions, there are potential limitations such as biases and training data gaps regardless of the utilization of RAG. Users may experience digital literacy barriers in medical text responses from the LLMs.³⁴ Retrieving appropriate data to answer user queries of different intents poses a challenge, as retrieval from different knowledge bases requires routing.³⁵ The RapidFuzz string matching the medication name failed to distinguish between drugs with similar names and thus caused most of the incorrect answers when benchmarking LLMs with context on the cannabinoid DDI dataset.⁶

Furthermore, the CDI chatbot system appears only able to address prompts accurately when there are a total of two drug names. Follow-up questions to an initial drug interaction query may lead the system to route to drug interaction information retrieval, forcing the LLM to rely on pre-trained knowledge. Developing resource-efficient agentic systems (capable of achieving outcomes independently) could potentially provide more intelligent routing systems.³⁶ The safety guardrails of the CDI chatbot system may not be absolute and therefore subject to limitations. The quality of web-based content was another primary limitation of the CDI chatbot due to the DuckDuckGo Search (DDGS) application programming interface (API) only providing snippets from relevant websites.³⁷ Additional research could include investigating comprehensive Search Engine Results Page (SERP) APIs and implementing systems to scrape the results links.

6. CONCLUSION

Prior messaging opportunities have largely described cannabinoids as a safer alternative to the opioids. However, this project also brings attention to the cannabinoid containing products (prescription, CBD oils, medical marijuana, unregulated adult use cannabis) and the unintended drug-drug interaction(s) of a cannabinoid affecting the metabolism of ANOTHER medication (e.g., warfarin).³⁸

The CDI chatbot, a second-generation iteration, is based on our prior research for the online resource CANNabinoid Drug Interaction Review (CANN-DIR®) <https://CANN-DIR.psu.edu> that has been translated into 11 languages and viewed in 101 countries.^{38,39} The CDI chatbot illustrates the potential of leveraging LLMs and drug knowledge databases to develop a clinical decision support tool that has demonstrated > 90% accuracy when addressing cannabinoid drug interaction queries and surpassing the baseline performance of all tested LLMs.

The CDI chatbot employs the Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct large language model (LLM), integrates natural language processing with the gte-large-en-v1.5 embedding model, and allows for hybrid information retrieval for database and web-based searches. The CDI chatbot implements a retrieval augmented generation (RAG) framework that allows for additional databases to be included without needing to retrain the LLM; therefore; allows for accurate, personalized, and formulating context-aware original output functioning as a cannabinoid clinical decision support tool. The CDI chatbot also integrates web search capabilities that further enhanced responses to general medical information queries.

Performance validation was conducted using a dataset of 1,369 multiple-choice questions across diverse medical topics with a RAG specific framework. Hybrid RAG systems like the CDI chatbot present a promising alternative in resource-constrained environments where fine-tuning is impractical. Future efforts could focus on expanding the drug interaction database and incorporating real-time updates. These findings demonstrate the CDI chatbot's benchmark performance and suggest the potential of RAG systems for clinical decision support applications.

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7. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

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